

A Study of Bodhisatta's Birth Scene Found at the KusināruÑ Pagoda in Mawlamyine

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to show the birth of the Bodhisatta from the life of the Gotama Buddha. The life of the Gotama Buddha, the founder of Buddhism is the most essential and indispensable for all Buddhists. The analytical studies of the contents of "The Bodhisatta's Birth scene found at the KusināruÑ Pagoda in Mawlamyine" were described by the PĒĀi literature and Sanskrit literature.

Introduction

The life of the Gotama Buddha starting from Sumedha's aspiration of Buddhahood and ending in distribution of the relics. Biography of the Gotama Buddha is found in PĒĀi literature and Sanskrit literature. In Sanskrit literature also, the biographical material are found both legendary and historical. This paper describes about the birth of the Gotama Buddha. In the birth of the Bodhisatta, Mahāmāyā Devī's journey to Devadaha City, LumbinĒ Garden of Sāla trees, the congregation of Devas and Brahmās , the Birth of the Bodhisatta , receiving the Bodhisatta successively by Brahmā, Deva and humans, the fearless roar, the Extraordinary acts of the Bodhisatta, their significance and the seven connatals of the Bodhisatta are included in it.

I would like to present on the analytical studies of the contents of "Bodhisatta's Birth scene found at KusināruÑ Pagoda in Mawlamyine" which was described by the PĒĀi literature and Sanskrit literature.

Mahāmāyā Devī's journey to Devadaha City

PĒĀi Literature describes the journey of MĒyĒ, the queen mother, to the LumbinĒ Garden. "When ten months of pregnancy came to completion, Queen SirimahĒ MĒyĒdevī had a desire to go to Devadaha, her native city, where her parents were residing. She asked King Suddhodana to allow her to go there. The king renovated the road to Devadaha from Kapilavatthu smooth and straight. It was like a road of Devas. He ordered one thousand of

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king's counselors to lift the golden palanquin to carry the queen. Thousands of retinue surrounded her along the journey. There was a royal garden called Lumbinī between the two cities. It was a forest of Sal trees. The flowers bloomed richly of every tree to the top. The queen wanted to enjoy herself in that pleasant forest. So, the king's counselors brought her to that garden".

According to the Lalitavithāra describes this event in a richly manner. "The queen mother, Māyā, was surrounded by well equipped chariots, elephants and 84,000 foot-men. 60,000 Sēkiya damsels followed the queen 400,000 relatives of king Suddhodana and 60,000 royal court performers accompanied the queen. There were singers of dancers. They sang songs of glory. Besides, young goddesses, mythical serpents, musician goddesses, and Asurēs, each consisted of 84000 also surrounded the queen. Thus surrounded, the queen went to the garden in an elegant chariot. The whole garden was fragrant with scented water and perfume. It was adorned with various Deva flowers. All the flower plants and trees bloomed and all the fruit trees bore fruits unseasonably. The Devas also created the Missaka garden and adorned it wonderfully".

Mahāvasthu describes the event in yet another way. "King Suddhodana ordered thus: let the garden be cleansed of all garbage quickly, let it be a beautiful and fragrant flower garden, let the whole garden be filled with fragrance, let the smooth breeze, filled with the scent of Tamēla leaves, run through out the garden, In this way the king let the garden renovated in a wonderful manner. Surrounded by a multitude of retinue, the queen arrived at the garden".

A study of these descriptions shows that King Suddhodana had tried his utmost to make the road to Devadaha and the Lumbinī Garden to be as pleasant as possible. Lalitavithāra describes this event in quite different way. It tells about the queen's journey in an especial manner. Her retinue included not only human beings but also Devas and mythical beings.

Lumbinī Garden of Sāla trees

Between Kapilavatthu and Devadaha cities, there was a grove of Sāla trees by the name of Lumbinī Garden frequented by people from both kingdoms for recreation. When Mahāmāyā Devī reached it, every Sāla tree in the grove was in full bloom from the bottom of the tree to the topmost branches.

Amidst flowers and twigs of Sāla trees swarms of bumblebees in five colours hummed, and flocks of birds of many species chirped, producing sweet melodious sounds. The whole Sāla grove was so delightful and enjoyable with special features that it might be likened to Cittalatā Garden of Sakka, the Deva King. It was also like a place constantly filled with the sounds of mirth and merriment at a feast well organized by a powerful king¹.

On account of the melodious sounds emanating from the female bees which were buzzing delightfully among the buds and flowers, the twigs and branches; which were excited with the intoxicating nectar produced by fragrant Sāla flowers; Lumbinī was very much like Nandavana Garden, the delight of Devas.

¹ Ja-a-I-61-62 , Ap-a-I-63, Bv-a-320

On seeing Lumbinī Garden of such immense splendours Mahāmāyā Devī felt a desire to amuse herself in it.

The ministers sought permission from King Suddhodana and with the royal consent they entered the garden carrying the Chief Queen on the golden palanquin.

The congregation of Devas and Brahmās

The moment Mahāmāyā Devī entered Lumbinī Garden, all Devas proclaimed with an uproar which reverberated throughout the ten thousand world-systems, "Today the Bodhisatta will be born from the lotus-like chamber of the mother's womb." The Devas and Brahmās from the ten thousand world-systems congregated, crowding the whole of this universe, bringing with them a large variety of auspicious treasures as gifts to pay homage with in celebration of the birth of the Bodhisatta. The vault of heaven was covered all over with their celestial white umbrellas and the entire universe resounded with their auspicious songs, celestial music and the sounds of conch shells blown by them.

As soon as Mahāmāyā Devī got into Lumbinī Garden, she felt a sudden urge to grasp with her hand a branch of the fully blooming Sāla tree, the trunk of which was straight and round. As if it were animate, the branch bent down itself like a cane stalk, made pliant by boiling, until it reached the palm of the queen, a marvelous event that stirred up the minds of many.

Queen Mahāmāyā Devī stood holding the Sāla branch that came down into the palm of her outstretched lovely right hand which was adorned with brand-new gold bracelets with her fingers shapely like a lotus stem, her finger-nails bright red like the colour of a parrot's beak. The great beauty of Queen Mahāmāyā Devī at that instant resembled the moon that newly emerges from the dark, somber clouds showing signs of impending rain or the lightning that dazzles in a momentary flash, or a celestial nymph who makes her appearance in Nandavana Garden.

The Birth Manner

Pāli Literature¹ describes the manner of the birth of the Future Buddha. Holding the Sāla branch, Queen Mahāmāyā Devī stood majestically in a dress of gold-threaded brocade and draped down to the tip of her feet in a full-length white embroidered shawl with exquisite patterns resembling the eyes of a carp. At that very moment she felt the unmistakable signs of the impending birth. Her retinue hastily cordoned off the area with curtains and withdrew. Instantaneously, the ten thousand world-systems together with the great ocean roared, quaked, and trembled like the potter's wheel. Devas and Brahmās acclaimed in joy and showered flowers from the sky; all musical instruments produced mellifluous melodies automatically. The entire universe became unveiled with unobstructed visibility in all directions. These and other strange, marvellous phenomena, thirty-two in all, occurred simultaneously to herald the birth of the Bodhisatta. As the flying precious jewel emerging from the top of Mount Vepulla hovers and then descends slowly on a readily placed receptacle, so the Bodhisatta magnificently adorned with major and minor physical marks, was delivered clean and pure from the stupa-like lotus-womb

of Mahāmayā Devī on Friday the full moon of Vesākha, a summer month in the year 68, Mahā Era, when the moon was in conjunction with the constellation Visākha.

Although other ordinary women gave birth to a child before ten months of pregnancy or after the completion of the ten months of pregnancy in a lying down posture, the royal queen mother gave birth in a standing posture. When other living beings, including men, were born, they were smeared with filthy excrement. But, when the Future Buddha was born, he was quite clean. The moment the Bodhisatta was born, two fountains of pure spring water, warm and cold, flowed down from the sky² and fell on the already pure and clean bodies of the Bodhisatta and the mother as a token of homage, thereby enabling them to adjust the heat and cold in their bodies.

From among the above mentioned subjects, there arise two versions. Regarding the tree to which the royal queen mother took hold of at the time of the birth, a comparison will be made between the version as contained in the Pāli records, such as TathĒgatuppatti and JĒtaka NidĒnakathĒ and the version as contained in the Sanskrit records, such as Lalita and MahĒvatthu. The Pāli records say that the royal mother took hold of the bough of the sal tree. But MahĒvatthu say that it was a fig tree. Lalita say that it was a "Plaksa tree". "Plaksa" in Sanskrit is equivalent to "Pilakkha" (a kind of banyan tree) in Pāli. Therefore, the Sanskrit version means to say that it was a fig tree.

Regarding the mode of birth Pāli literatures state that the child was born in a natural way while the mother was in standing posture. But Lalita, MahĒvatthu and Buddhacarita³ say that the son was not born in an ordinary humanly way. They state that while the mother was standing, the son automatically broke through the right ribs of the mother. This statement is unreasonable and mythical. It is against the law of Nature's way.

Receiving the Bodhisatta successively by Brahmās, Devas and humans

Pāli Literature⁴ mentions that as soon as the Bodhisatta came out the womb of the queen mother, he was received by the four SuddhĒvĒsa Brahmās, with a "golden net". Then he was received by the four great Deva kings with the skin of a black leopard. He was again received by the people with a fabulous white cloth. Then the Future Buddha looked to the east and looked at all the ten directions. He found no one like him. Then, facing north, he moved seven steps forward. He roared such expressions as "I am the noblest in the world.".

¹ Ja-a-I-61-62, Ap-a-I-63, Bv-a-320

D-II-11-13, M-III-96, D-a-II-27-34, M-a-III-222, Ja-a-I-61-67, Ap-a-I-63-69, Bv-a-319-324.

The PiĒaka scriptures say that the Future Buddha was born from the vagina of the royal queen mother. The feet started to come out when he was born

Bv-a-319-321, Ja-a-I-60-61, Ap-a-I-62-63

The hot and cold streams did not flow from the sky to wash away the filth from the body of the Future Buddha, not for drinking water nor for other utility preposes. It was only for him to play with.

³ Lal-Tran-128, Mvu-pt II-16-17, Buddha-c-Tran-27

LalitavithĒra, MahĒvatthu and Buddhacarita state that while the mother was standing, the son automatically broke through the right ribs of the mother.

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D-II-11-13, M-III-96, D-a-II-27-34, M-a-III-222, Ja-a-I-61-67, Ap-a-I-63-69, Bv-a-319-324.

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Bv-a-319-321, Ja-a-I-60-61, Ap-a-I-62-63

Then, after leaving the hands of the people, the Bodhisatta stood firmly on his feet with the soles like those of a golden footwear, and touching the ground fully and squarely, he looked towards the eastern direction. As he did so, thousands of world-systems in the east became one continuous stretch of open space without any barrier or boundary between one another. The Devas and human beings in the eastern quarter most respectfully paid homage to the Bodhisatta with perfumes, flowers, etc and said:

Then the Future Buddha looked to the east and looked at all the ten directions. He found no one like him. Then, facing north, he moved seven steps forward. He roared such expressions as "I am the noblest in the world.".

"O Noble Man, there is no one in this eastern direction who is your equal. How can there be anyone who is superior to you? "

Similarly, the Bodhisatta looked out in the rest of the ten directions- the four cardinals, the four intermediate, the downward and the upward directions- one after another. He saw no one equal to him in all these quarters. Thereupon, he faced northward from where he stood and took seven steps forward.

The Bodhisatta was followed by Mahā Brahmā, King of Brahmās, giving cover to him with the white umbrella and by Deva Suyāma holding a fly-flap made of a yak tail. Other Devas with the remaining emblems of royalty such as the footwear, the sword and the crown also followed him from behind. The celestial beings in this procession were not visible to the people who could see only the regalia.

But Lalitavithāra and Mahāvathu describe this event in a different way. They state that Sakka and the King of Brahmās received the child in a robe of Deva. While the Bodhisatta was still in the womb of the mother, he resided in a building called "Ratanāyāha". The Brahmās took that building to their abode and enshrined in a stupa for worship. The Bodhisatta came out of the mother's womb and stepped on the ground. A Lotus cropped up under each step. The kings of the mythical serpents sprinkled the child with hot and cold water. The fan made of yak¹ tail and the white umbrellas automatically appeared above the child. He looked at the six directions without any fear. He uttered such expressions as "I am the noblest in the world"²

It can be said that the Lalita's statements are basically similar to other texts. But it contains a miraculous phenomenon. "During his sojourn for ten months in the mother's womb, he resided in the building called "Ratanāyāha". As soon as he was born, the Brahmās took away that building to their plane and enshrined it in a stupa for worship".

The texts are at variance in describing about the seven steps, moved by the Future Buddha soon after his birth. Tathāgatuppatti, Jētaka Nidānakathā, Buddha-carita and Jinacarita mention that the Future Buddha moved seven steps towards the north. But Lalitavithāra says that he moved seven steps each towards the six directions. And Mahāvathu did not mention about the direction to which he moved. It just says that he

¹ camara 'yak' is a four-footed native animal who loves his tail; therefore when the tail is stuck with the bush it does not struggle to be free from the bush.

² Lal-TRAN-128-146 , Mvu-pt-II-16-17

looked at the world and laughed vehemently. But the texts agree with mentioning about the utterance of the Bodhisatta.

Special points for note:⁵

When the Bodhisatta walked he did so on the natural ground, but to the human beings he appeared to be walking through the air. The Bodhisatta walked 'au natural' without any clothes on, but to the human beings he appeared to be walking fully clad. Only as a new born child the Bodhisatta walked, but to the human beings he appeared to be sixteen years old.

While the Bodhisatta took his steps the great Brahmās followed and shaded him with the royal white umbrella measuring three Yojanas. So did the great Brahmās from the remaining worlds with their white umbrellas of the same size. Thus the whole universe was fully covered by white umbrellas resembling the garlands of white blooms.

The ten thousand *Suyāma* Devas living in the ten thousand world-systems stood holding individually their yak-tail fly-flaps; the ten thousand *Santusita* Devas of the same world-systems stood, holding their ruby-studded round fans, all swinging their fly-flaps and round fans right up to the mountain sides on the edge of the universe.

In the same way, the ten thousand *Sakkas* residing in the ten thousand world-systems stood blowing ten thousand conches.

All other *Deva* stood in like manner, some carrying flowers of gold while others carrying natural flowers or scintillating glass flowers (flowers glittering like glass); some carrying flaps and banners, while others carrying gem-studded objects of offering. Female deities with various gifts in their hands also stood crowding the entire universe.

While the phenomenal display of homage which was like the *Rasāyana*, gratifying sight for the eye was in progress, while thousands of conches were being blown melodiously by human and *Devas*, while celestial and terrestrial musical instruments were being played and female deities were joyfully dancing, the Bodhisatta halted after taking seven steps in the northward direction.

At that moment all the *Brahmās*, *Devas* and humans maintained complete silence, waiting expectantly with the thought "What is the Bodhisatta going to say?"

The fearless roar⁶

When he halted after taking the seven steps in the direction of north the Bodhisatta made a fearless roar to be heard simultaneously by all throughout the entire ten thousand world-systems as follows;

(a) "Aggo'hañ asmi lokassa!"

"I am the most superior among the living beings of the three worlds",

(b) "Jeṃho'hañ asmi lokassa!"

⁵ The great Chronical of Buddhas Vol II, Part I- 28-29

⁶ The great Chronical of Buddhas Vol II, Part I - 29-30

"I am the greatest among the living beings of the three worlds",

(c) "Seṭṭho'' haÑ asmi lokassa!"

"I am the most exalted among the living beings of the three worlds!",

(d) "AyaÑ antimā jāti!"

"This is my last birth!",

(e) "Natthi dāni punabbhavo!"

"There are no more rebirths for me!"

When the Bodhisatta made this bold speech, there was no one capable of challenging or rebutting him, whole multitude of Brahmās, Devas and humans had to tender their felicitations.

The extraordinary acts of the Bodhisatta and their significance⁷

Out of the extraordinary acts at the time of the Bodhisatta's birth, the following were omens, each with its significance.

- (1) The Bodhisatta's firm standing with both feet evenly on the earth's surface was the omen signifying his future attainment of the four bases of Psychic Power (Iddhipāda);
- (2) The Bodhisatta's facing northwards was the omen signifying his future supremacy over all living beings;
- (3) The Bodhisatta's taking seven steps was the omen signifying his future attainment of the seven Constituents of Enlightenment, the Jewel of the Dhamma;
- (4) The Bodhisatta's having the cool shade of the celestial white umbrella was the omen signifying his future attainment of the fruition of Arahatsip;
- (5) The Bodhisatta's acquisition of the five emblems of royalty was the omen signifying his future attainment of the five kinds of Emancipation (Vimutti), namely,
 - Emancipation through performance of meritorious deeds of sensuous sphere (Tada-ga Vimutti);
 - Emancipation through attainment of Jhānas (Vikkhambhana Vimutti);
 - Emancipation through attainment of the Paths (Samuccheda Vimutti);
 - Emancipation through attainment of Fruitions (Paḷipassaddhi Vimutti);
 - Emancipation through attainment of Nibbāna (NissaraṀa Vimutti);
- (6) The Bodhisatta's seeing in the ten directions without any obstruction was the omen signifying his future attainment of Unobstructed Knowledge (AnāvaraṀa ©āṀa)

⁷ The great Chronical of Buddhas Vol II, Part I - 30-31

- (7) The Bodhisatta's fearless roar, "I am the most superior, the greatest and the most exalted!", was the omen signifying his future turning of the Wheel of the Dhamma (Dhamma Cakka) which no Brahmās, Devas or human beings are capable of halting or retarding its process;
- (8) The Bodhisatta's fearless roar, "This is my last birth!; There is no more rebirth for me!," was the omen signifying his future attainment of Nibbāna with no remaining physical and mental aggregates (Anupādisesa)

The three existences in which the Bodhisatta spoke at birth⁸

The Bodhisatta spoke immediately after his birth, not only in this last existence as Prince Siddhattha, but also when he was born to become Mahosadha the Wise, and when he was born to become King Vessantara. Hence there were three existences in which he spoke at birth.

Brief explanation : (1) In his existence as Mahosadha the Wise, the Bodhisatta came out of the mother's womb, holding a piece of sandalwood which had been placed in his hand by Sakka, King of Devas. The mother on seeing the object in the hand of her newly born baby asked, "My dear son, what have you brought in your hand?" "O mother, it is medicine," answered the Bodhisatta.

He was thus initially named Osadha Kumāra meaning "Medicine Boy." The medicine was carefully stored in a jar. All patients who came with all kinds of ailment, such as blindness, deafness, etc, were cured with that medicine, beginning with the Bodhisatta's wealthy father SirivaĒhāna, who was cured of his headache. Thus because of the great efficacy of his medicine, the youthful Bodhisatta later came to be popularly known as Mahosadha, the young possessor of the most efficacious medicine.

(2) In the existence of the Bodhisatta as King Vessantara also, the moment he was born he extended his right hand with open palm and said, "O mother, what do you have in your golden palace that I can give in charity." The mother answered, "My dear son, you are born to wealth in this golden palace." Then the mother took the child's open hand, placed it on her palm and put a bag of one thousand silver pieces. Thus the Bodhisatta also spoke at birth in the existence of King Vessantara.

(3) As has been narrated above, in his last existence as Prince Siddhattha, the Bodhisatta made the fearless roar the moment he was born.

These are the three existences in which the Bodhisatta spoke immediately after the mother had given birth to him.

⁸ The great Chronical of Buddhas Vol II, Part I - 31-32

The phenomenal events at the Bodhisatta's birth and what they presaged⁹

Also at the moment of the birth of the Bodhisatta certain events manifested clearly.

(1) At the time of the birth of the Bodhisatta the ten thousand world-systems quaked.

This was the omen presaging his attainment of Omniscience.

(2) Deva and Brahmās living in the ten thousand world-systems congregated in this universe.

This was the omen presaging the assembly of Deva and Brahmās for listening to the Discourse of the wheel of Dhamma when delivered.

(3) The Brahmās and Devas were the first to receive the Bodhisatta at the time of his birth.

This was the omen presaging his attainment of the four R|pāvacara Jhānas.

(4) The human beings received the new born Bodhisatta after the Deva and Brahmās and Devas.

This was the omen presaging his attainment of the four Ar|pāvacara Jhānas.

(5) The stringed instruments such as harps made sound of music without being played.

This was the omen presaging his attainment of the nine Anupubba Vihāra Samāpatti consisting of the four R|pāvacara-Samāpatti, the four Ar|pāvacara-Samāpatti and Nirodha-Samāpatti.

(6) Leather instruments such as big and small drums made sound of music without being played.

This was the omen presaging his beating of the most sacred drum of Dhamma to be heard by humans and Devas alike.

(7) Prisons and fetters keeping men in bondage broke up into pieces.

This was the omen presaging his complete elimination of the conceited notion of 'I'.

(8) All kinds of diseases afflicting the sick disappeared like the dirt on copper when washed away by acid.

This was the omen presaging his attainment by human beings of the four Noble Truths, eradication of all suffering of Saṅsāra.

(9) The blind since birth could see all forms and colours as do normal people.

This was the omen presaging the acquisition by human beings of the Divine Eye (Dibbacakkhu).

(10) The deaf since birth could hear all sounds as do normal people.

This was the omen presaging the acquisition by human beings of the Divine Ear (Dibbasota).

⁹ The great Chronical of Buddhas Vol II, Part I - 32-37

(11) The cripple gained healthy legs and could walk about.

This was the omen presaging the acquisition by human beings of the four Bases of Psychic Power (Iddhipādas).

(12) The dumb since birth gained mindfulness and could speak.

This was the omen presaging the acquisition of the four Methods of Steadfast Mindfulness (Satipaṭṭhāna).

(13) Ships on perilous voyages abroad reached their respective havens.

This was the omen presaging the acquisition of the fourfold Analytical Knowledge (Paṭisambhidā ṅāṇa).

(14) All kind of precious gems, both celestial and terrestrial, glittered most brilliantly.

This was the omen presaging the acquisition of the light of Dhamma; it was the omen presaging the brilliant glory of the Buddha who disseminated the light of Dhamma to those who were bent on receiving it.

(15) Loving kindness pervaded among all beings who were at enmity with one another.

This was the omen presaging the attainment of four Sublime States (Brahmavihāra)

(16) The hell-fires were extinguished.

This was the omen presaging the cessation of eleven kinds of fires such as greed, anger, etc.

(17) There appeared light in the Lokantarika hells which normally are in total darkness.

This was the omen presaging the ability to dispel the darkness of ignorance and to shed the light of Wisdom.

(18) The river water which had been perennially flowing ceased to flow.

This was the omen presaging the acquisition of Fourfold Confidence (Catuvesārajja ṅāṇa)

(19) All the waters in the great ocean turned sweet in taste.

This was the omen presaging the acquisition of unique sweet taste of peace resulting from the cessation of defilements.

(20) Instead of stormy winds, light winds blew cool and pleasant.

This was the omen presaging the disappearance of the sixty-two kinds of wrong beliefs.

(21) All kinds of birds in the sky or on top of trees or mountains alighted to the ground.

This was the omen presaging the life-long taking of refuge (in the Triple Gem) by human beings after listening to the teaching of the Buddha.

(22) The moon shone forth far brighter than ever before.

This was the omen presaging the delighted mood of human beings.

(23) The sun being of moderate heat and clear radiance brought clement weather.

This was the omen presaging the physical and mental happiness of human beings.

(24) The Devas standing at the doorways of their mansions slapped their arms with the other hands, whisted and flung their clothes in merriment.

This was the omen presaging his attainment of Omniscient Buddhahood and making solemn utterance of joy.

(25) Torrential rain fell all over the four continents.

This was the omen presaging the heavy Dhamma rain of Deathlessness which fell with the great force of wisdom.

(26) All human beings felt no hunger.

This was the omen presaging their attainment of the Deathless Dhamma of *Kāyagatāsati* which is mindfulness related to the body, or freedom from hunger for defilements after enjoying the Deathless food of *Kāyagatāsati* .

(27) All human beings felt no thirst.

This was the omen presaging their attainment of the bliss of the Fruition of Arahatsip.

(28) Closed doors burst open by themselves.

This was the omen presaging the opening up of the gates of *Nibbāna* which is the eightfold Noble Path.

(29) Flower trees and fruit trees bore flowers and fruits respectively.

This was the omen presaging the people's bearing the flowers of Emancipation (*Vimutti*) and the fruits of the Noble Ones (*Ariyaphala*)

(30) All the ten thousand world-systems were covered with the one only flower-banner. The ten thousand world-systems were covered with the banner of victory.

This was the omen presaging the overspreading by the flower-banner, i.e, the Noble Path.

Moreover, the showering of exquisite flowers and exceedingly fragrant flowers, the brightness of stars and constellations even in sunlight, the appearance of springs of pure clean water, the coming out of burrowing animals from their places, the absence of greed, hate and bewilderment, the absence of clouds of dust from the ground, the absence of obnoxious smells, the pervasion of celestial perfumes, the clear visibility of *Rūpa Brahmās* to human beings, the absence of birth and death of human beings and other phenomena occurred distinctly. The occurrence of these phenomena constituted omens presaging the Buddha's attainment of attributes other than those mentioned above.

The seven connatals of the Bodhisatta¹⁰

At that precise moment of the birth of the Bodhisatta, the following seven were born simultaneously:

- (1) Princess Yasodharā, also named Baddakaccānā, mother of Prince Rāhula;
- (2) Prince Ānandā;
- (3) Minister Channa;
- (4) Minister Kāḷudāyī;
- (5) Royal stallion Kaḷēka
- (6) Mahā Bodhi or Assattha Bodhi Tree; and
- (7) Four jars of gold.

Since they were born or coming into being at the same time as the Bodhisatta, they were known as the seven connatals of the Bodhisatta of these seven:

- (1) princess Yasodharā Baddakaccānā was born of Suppabuddha, King of Devadaha City, and Queen Amittā;
- (2) Prince Ānandā was the son of the Sakyan Amittodana, younger brother of King Suddhodana;
- (3) The Mahā Bodhi Tree grew at the center of the site of victory where the Buddha attained Enlightenment in Uruvelā forest of the Middle Country;
- (4) The four large jars of gold appeared within the precincts of the palace of Kapilavatthu City, of these four ;
 - (a) one was named Sankha, the diameter of its brim being one gāvuta ;
 - (b) another was named Ela, , the diameter of its brim being two gāvutas;
 - (c) the third was named Uppala, , the diameter of its brim being three gāvutas;
 - (d) the last one named Puḷka, , the diameter of its brim being four gāvutas, equivalent to one yojana.

When some gold was taken out of these four jars, they became replenished; there was no trace of any loss. (The account of these four jars of gold is given in the exposition of the Ca-kī Sutta of the Majjhimapaṭiṣāya Commentary, and also in the exposition of the Soḷadaḷā Sutta of the Dīgha Nikāya Sīlakkhandha vagga Commentary.)

The order of the name of the seven birth-mates of the Bodhisatta given above is that contained in the Commentaris on the Jātaka and the Buddhavaṅsa and also in the exposition of the Mahāpadāna Sutta of the Dīgha Nikāya Mahāvagga Commentary.

¹⁰ The great Chronical of Buddhas Vol II, Part I - 38

In the exposition of the story of *Kāṅudāyē* in the A-guttara Commentary and also in the exposition of the story of *Rāhula* in the *Vinaya Sārattha Dēpanē* *ēkā*, *Ānanda*'s name has been left out from the list. It includes (1) Bodhi Tree, (2) *Yasodharā*, (3) The four jars of gold, (4) Royal elephant named *Ārohanīya*, (5) *KaŌēaka* the steed, (6) Minister *Channa*, (7) Minister *Kāṅudāyē*, in that order.

Pāli Literature¹¹ continues to say about the seven birth-mates at the moment of the birth of the Future Buddha. They were 1. *Yasodharē*, mother of *Rēhulē*, 2. *Shin Ānandē*, 3. *Channa* the counselor, 4. *Kēludēyē* 5. *KaŌēaka* the horse, 6. *Mahēbodhi* tree and 7. four Jars of Gold.

*Tathēgatuppatti*¹², *Buddhavaṅsa AŌhakatthē*¹³, *Jētaka AŌhakatthē*, (Vol: II)¹⁴ and *Dēghanikēya Mahēvagga AŌha-kathē*¹⁵ are in agreement in describing the seven birth mates. But *Theragēthē AŌhakatthē* (Vol. II)¹⁶ and *Sērattha ēkē* (Vol. III)¹⁷ mention the seven birth-mates thus: 1. *Mahēbodhi* tree, 2. *Yasodharē*, 3. four Jars of Gold, 4. the Elephant 5. the Horse, 6. *Channa* and 7. *Kēludēyi*. (The Elephant is mentioned in place of *Shin Ānandē*.)

But *Lalitavithēra* mentions nine birth-mates. They were: 1. 500 young boys, 2. 10,000 *Sēkiya* damsels, headed by *Yasodharē*, 3. 800 slave girls, 4. 800 slave boys, headed by *Channa*, 5. 1000 horses, headed by *KaŌēika*, 6. 5000 elephants of *pi-gala* species, 7. 5000 cows, 8. 500 gardens and 9. 5000 jars of gold.¹⁸

Again, the *Mahēvatthu* mentions in a different way. Somewhat as : 1. *Bodhi* bunyan tree, 2. 500 *Sēkiya* princes, led by *sundarananda*, 3. 500 service men, led by *channa*, 4. 500 horses, led by *KaŌēika*, 5. sandal wood forest, 6. *yasodharē* 7. 500 elephants, led by *candana* and 8. 500 jars of gold.¹⁹

Thus, it is found that the texts mention about the birth-mates in a varied way. However, *Yasodhara*, *channa*, *kaŌēaka* and the jars of gold are found to be mentioned concurrently in the texts.

Thus, it is found that the texts mention about the birth-mates in a varied way. However, *Yasodhara*, *channa*, *kaŌēaka* and the jars of gold are found to be mentioned concurrently in the texts.

¹¹ Ja-a-I-61-62, Ap-a-I-63, Bv-a-320

D-II-11-13, M-III-96, D-a-II-27-34, M-a-III-222, Ja-a-I-61-67, Ap-a-I-63-69, Bv-a-319-324.

The *PiŌaka* scriptures say that the Future Buddha was born from the vagina of the royal queen mother. The feet started to come out when he was born.

¹² Tu-From reverse side of folio '-e' to obverse side of folio '-ē'

Ja-a-I-63, Bv-a-322, D-a-II-18

¹³ Bv-a-63

¹⁴ Ja-a-I-63

¹⁵ D-a-II-18

¹⁶ Th-a-II-165

¹⁷ Sp-®-III-244

¹⁸ Lal-Tran-146-147

¹⁹ Mvu-Pt-II, 22

Conclusion

In this way it is found that the Bodhisatta's Birth scene has been put on records by various forms. Here, a little discrepancy is found. Regarding the mode of birth, Pāli literatures state that the child was born in a natural way while the mother was in standing posture. But Sanskrit literatures say that the son was not born in an ordinary humanly way. They state that while the mother was standing, the son automatically broke through the right ribs of the mother. This statement is unreasonable and mythical. It is against the law of Nature's way. But, it is to be considered that only the statements made by such Pāli literature records are logical and not contrary to the majority views.

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